

SPATIAL VARIATIONS IN WORK PARTICIPATION RATE IN HIMACHAL PRADESH: A DISTRICT LEVEL STUDY

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Abstract:

Work participation is an important indicator for understanding the socio-economic development of various segments of the population of a country. It is the interest of the society to make full and most effective use of its human resources. The full benefit of development of development can only be realized with people's participation and the economic role of women cannot be isolated from the total framework of development. In the present paper an attempt has been made to study spatial variations in work participation in the state of Himachal Pradesh. The district wise secondary data of working population and total population have been collected from Census of India, 2011. District wise percentage of total workers to total population by gender have been calculated by field calculator using QGIS and presented in tabular form and choropleth maps. The study reveals that total work participation rate on an average in 2001 was 49.20 percent which has increased to 51.85 percent in 2011. The male work participation rate was 54.62 percent in 2001 which has increased to 58.69 percent in 2011. Similarly the female work participation rate has increased from 43.67 to 44.82 percent during the same period. The study also shows that during 2011 there is a considerable spatial variation in the male and female work participation rate being highest in Kinnaur district and lowest in Una district in both cases.

Key Words: Work Participation, Human Resources, Development, Himachal Pradesh, Secondary Data, Working Population, Spatial Variation, Female Work Participation Rate

Introduction:

India has experienced rapid economic growth, structural shifts in the economy, increase in educational attainment levels and rapid urbanization in the last twenty five years. Work participation is an important indicator for understanding the socio-economic development of various segments of the population of a country. It is the interest of the society to make full and most effective use of its human resources. The full benefit of development of development can only be realized with people's participation and the economic role of women cannot be isolated from the total framework of development. However, Age, education, and marital status all had a substantial impact on women's economic engagement (Naqvi and Shahnaz, 2002). Women's income rates and education levels are positively associated to labour force participation rates (Aly and Quisi, 1996).

The Study Area

Extending from 30⁰22'40''N to 33⁰12'40''N latitudes and 75⁰45'55''E to 79⁰04'20''E longitudes, the study area is the state of Himachal Pradesh (Figure 1). The altitudes in the Pradesh, a wholly mountainous region in the lap of Himalayas range from 350 meters to 6975 meters above mean sea level. It is bordered by Jammu & Kashmir to the north, Punjab to the west, Haryana to the south, and Uttarakhand to the southwest.

According to Surveyor General of India, the total area of Himachal Pradesh is 55673 square Kilometer which is divided into twelve administrative districts. Out of this total area, 32,271 square Kilometer is measured area according to revenue records of the Pradesh. Area-wise, Hamirpur is the smallest district of the Himachal Pradesh which covers an area of 1,118 square Kilometer (2.01%) and Lahaul-Spiti has the largest area of 13,835 square Kilometer (24.85%).

The Kinnaur and Lahaul-Spiti district has on the Eastern boundary whereas Tibet is on western part, now it is a part of China. Although a relatively small state within the Indian Union, it manifests with ranges in altitudes, climate and geology. Whilst significant areas of the state are mountainous and above the tree line, including the "cold desert" areas, it also includes temperate and sub - tropical zones. Lahul and Spiti is a big district having international boundary with Tibet. In present times Himachal Pradesh has emerged as the socially and economically most developed state of the Indian union.

Figure 1

Objectives of the Study:

In the present paper an attempt has been made to study spatial variations in work participation rate by gender in the state of Himachal Pradesh.

Method and Material:

The present study is based on secondary data. The data pertaining to district level working population and total population has been collected from Census of India, 2011. District wise work participation rate by gender is calculated as percentage of total workers to total population by field calculator using QGIS and presented in tabular form and choropleth maps.

Results and Discussion:

Table 1: Himachal Pradesh Work Participation Rate 2011

S.No	District Name	Percentage of Work Participation		
		Total	Male	Female
1	Mandi	57.28	59.72	54.85
2	Kinnaur	66.90	73.22	59.70
3	Solan	51.48	61.54	40.04
4	Sirmaur	52.86	61.31	43.65
5	Shimla	52.94	60.85	44.30

6	Bilaspur	53.90	57.87	49.86
7	Lahaul-Spiti	61.13	64.88	56.97
8	Una	41.32	53.70	28.64
9	Kullu	61.45	66.01	56.60
10	Chamba	56.65	60.76	52.47
11	Kangra	44.71	53.79	35.74
12	Hamirpur	53.20	54.69	51.83
Total		51.85	58.69	44.82

Total work participation rate in Himachal Pradesh on an average in 2001 was 49.20 percent (Census of India, 2001) which has increased to 51.85 percent in 2011. Table 1 and Figure 2 show that there is a considerable spatial variation in total work participation rate in 2011. The higher percentage of work participation is found in Kinnaur district followed by Kullu and Lahaul-Spiti districts. Mandi, Chamba, Bilaspur, Hamirpur, Shimla and Sirmaur are other districts having total work participation rate more than the state average. Lower percentage of work participation is recorded in Una district followed by Kangra and Solan districts.

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Similarly, the female work participation rate has increased from 43.67 to 44.82 percent during the same period. Table 1 and Figure 3 exhibit that the higher percentage of female work participation in 2011 is found in Kinnaur district followed by Lahaul-Spiti and Kullu district and lower percentage of work participation is recorded in Una district followed by Kangra district. Solan, Sirmaur and Shimla are other districts having total work participation rate less than the state average.

The male work participation rate was 54.62 percent in 2001 which has increased to 58.69 percent in 2011. It is evident from Table 1 and Figure 4 that in 2011 the higher percentage of male work participation is found in Kinnaur district followed by Kullu and Lahaul-Spiti districts, lower percentage of male work participation is noted in Una district followed by Kangra district. Hamirpur and Bilaspur are other districts having male work participation rate less than the state average.

Conclusion:

Work participation rate in Himachal Pradesh has increased in 2011 as compared to 2001. During 2011, there is a considerable spatial variation in the male and female work participation rate in the state being highest in Kinnaur district and lowest in Una district in both cases.

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